

Nudging Toward Sustainable Food Consumption at University Canteens: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: This systematic literature review and meta-analysis investigated the effectiveness of the nudging approach toward sustainable food consumption in the university canteen context.

Methods: The systematic literature search was carried out in 5 databases, Web of Science, PubMed, Scopus, ProQuest, and the Royal Library, identifying 14 eligible studies and selecting 9 articles containing adequate information for meta-analysis. The nudging strategies were classified using the typology of interventions in the proximal physical microenvironments framework that resulted in 5 different intervention types: availability, position, size, presentation, and information that belonged to either intervention class-altering properties or placement.

Results: The study identified presentation, availability, and information as the most promising nudge intervention for achieving sustainable food consumption at the university canteen or similar settings. Nudging by altering the properties had a small effect size ($d = 0.16$), and nudging by altering placement showed a medium effect size ($d = 0.21$).

Discussion: Nudging interventions implemented after understanding consumers' current behavior showed positive effectiveness toward sustainable food consumption rather than implementing random nudges.

Conclusions and Implications: It is important that future studies aim to achieve sustainable food consumption by understanding canteen user food preferences and food choice motives before designing a nudging strategy.

Key Words: nudging, sustainable food consumption, systematic literature review, meta-analysis, university canteen (*J Nutr Educ Behav.* 2023;55:894–904.)

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INTRODUCTION

The global food system is complex, and currently, it is a significant contributor to global warming, with an estimated 37% of greenhouse gas emissions.^{1,2} According to the United Nations (UN), the environmental impact of the food systems can be significantly reduced through a shift

toward responsible production and consumption.³ As a result, the concept of a sustainable diet and sustainable food system is gaining attention and is increasingly explored in research and international politics.^{4,5}

According to the Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO), sustainable diets have low environmental impacts that contribute to food and nutrition

security and healthy life for present and future generations.⁶ The current food consumption pattern is unsustainable and negatively influences human and planetary health.^{7–9} However, policymakers and civil society leaders are approaching different strategies to promote sustainable food consumption and to achieve the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by 2050. Government policies and recommendations are being used in interventions to promote sustainable food consumption in public food spaces.^{10–13}

Nudging is a useful and often cost-effective approach that aims to create behavioral change in a predictive way without restricting the freedom of choice.^{14–16} It is an effective way for policymakers to design and evaluate food-related policy instruments.¹⁶ The nudging approach does

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not replace laws, regulations, or economic instruments but allows behavioral observation integration into the policy implementation.¹⁷ Furthermore, nudging may be applied to reach policy goals such as the new dietary guidelines published by the Danish government.^{18,19}

Interventions using nudging strategies are significantly nonobtrusive and do not require much cognitive effort to trigger consumer response in various settings.^{20,21} It steers consumer behavior in a preferred direction that can play a crucial role, for instance, in motivating consumers toward sustainable food consumption.^{22,23} Importantly, nudges are highlighted in the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change's Sixth Assessment Report as having slightly positive transformational potential and environmental effects and highly enabling effects on other food policies.²⁴ Moreover, the latest Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change's report included nudging within the feasible strategies with positive mitigation potential for combating climate change and achieving the SDGs.²⁴

Sustainable consumption (optimal use of resources to minimize the environmental impact) and proenvironmental behavior (behavior to reduce the adverse effects on the environment) could be promoted widely by applying a nudging approach to motivating consumers toward consuming environmentally friendly products.^{23,25} Previous systematic reviews have addressed implementing nudging strategies to promote sustainable behavior through the food supply chain,¹⁹ healthy food choices,²⁶ food waste behaviors,²⁷ and sustainable protein consumption (meat substitutes and alternative protein).²⁸ The article by Ferrari et al¹⁹ identified the effectiveness of green nudges in promoting environmentally sustainable behaviors among food supply chain actors (producers and consumers) in a broader context. However, the authors highlighted a need for more in-depth investigations to understand the effectiveness of different nudging strategies in a specific setting, as nudges may influence specific food chain actors differently.

At the consumer level, nudges effectively achieve the desired healthy eating behavior.²⁹ For instance, previous research has shown that altering placement had a modest effect on choosing fruits and vegetables (Cohen's $d = 0.3$).³⁰ Furthermore, changing portion size showed increased consumption of healthy items (Cohen's $d = 0.45$),³¹ and modification of the plate size seems to have a large effect on calorie intake (Cohen's $d = 0.7$).³² However, nudges are difficult to upscale to food service and may have little effect, as observed when applying a default nudging intervention—setting a dish by labeling it as the dish-of-the-day to reduce meat consumption by promoting novel plant-based alternatives as a replacement. The default nudging intervention did not affect food service when choices were among familiar and similar dishes.³³ Still, it was effective when choices were made between unfamiliar dishes in a restaurant setting.³⁴

Canteen meals are an essential part of the diet for young adults. As the young population enters university, they become more explorative and get influenced by different social environments, which may lead to poor dietary practices.^{35,36} Furthermore, it is a setting in which a large population of young adults spends their ample time, and the food environment at the university canteen has the potential to play a crucial role in shaping their eating behavior.^{37,38} Most health beliefs and practices are developed during young adulthood, shaping their and their family's lifestyle.^{39,40}

Overall, the main objective of this study is to systemize and synthesize the findings of recent research on nudging approaches to promote sustainable food consumption in university canteens. Furthermore, it aims to quantify the effectiveness of different nudging approaches for promoting sustainable food consumption in university canteens and their heterogeneity.

METHODS AND DATA

A systematic review was performed to select articles that applied nudges to

motivate dietary transitions in university canteens, followed by a meta-analysis to estimate its effect size. The systematic review follows the approach of Littell et al⁴¹ to effectively locate and synthesize the research by carefully assessing the quality of the research. The meta-analysis summarizes the effect sizes reported in different studies and corrects errors and biases in the research. The research follows the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines.⁴²

The literature search was conducted in December 2021 and included all records with titles and abstracts using the following string: “nudge*” AND “sustain*” AND “food consumption” AND (“university*” OR “campus”) AND (“canteen” OR “café”). The search was conducted using the following databases: Web of Science, Scopus, PubMed, the Royal Library, and ProQuest. The search string was adapted to the syntax of each database. Sustainable food consumption is an umbrella concept for sustainable food consumption behavior, covering various aspects such as proenvironmental behavior related to food, climate-friendly food choices, green food consumption, and ethical food consumption.⁴³ Therefore, articles that promote sustainable food consumption were selected by including ecolabels, climate labels, meat reduction, and portion-size sustainable dietary choices.

The systematic literature review included peer-reviewed articles published in English between 2011 and 2021. In addition, articles implementing a nudging approach to promote sustainable food consumption were included. The review included randomized control trials and interventional studies conducted in university contexts such as cafeterias, restaurants, dining halls, and canteens. The meta-analysis included articles with sufficient statistical data for effect size calculation (ie, the total number of participants, P , and effect direction).⁴⁴

Furthermore, the review excluded review articles, book chapters, dissertations, work-in-progress or papers-in-progress, articles without access to full texts, interventions not conducted at

the university canteen, not using the nudging approach, not focusing on sustainable food consumption, and not being peer-reviewed. Studies not specifying the total number of participants, *P*, and effect direction were excluded from the meta-analysis.

The articles were selected on the basis of the defined inclusion and exclusion criteria. Titles and abstracts were screened, and full texts were reviewed for relevant articles. Altogether, 250 articles were excluded after refining the inclusion and exclusion criteria. This resulted in 32 articles that were further screened and excluded, if not peer-reviewed, works on progress and dissertation/thesis. The title and abstract were reviewed by 2 reviewers, identifying 14 articles for the systematic literature review. The selected articles were screened thoroughly to determine

the eligibility for the article on the basis of the inclusion criteria. Out of these 14 articles, only 9 were included in the meta-analysis as they provided sufficient statistical data for effect size calculation. The PRISMA flow diagram illustrates the screening criteria for selecting the articles (Figure).

Descriptive data of the final set of 14 selected articles comprising study participants, country of study, year of data collection, intervention strategy, outcome measured, the applied method for data analysis, and findings on the effectiveness of nudging applied.

The typology of interventions in the proximal physical microenvironments (TIPPE) framework was used to identify the fundamental concept of the nudging strategies applied. The purpose of using this framework is to

classify and describe the effects of nudging intervention.⁴⁵ The framework identifies placement (change of environment) and properties (characteristics of the product) as 2 different classes further described according to 6 different intervention types (availability, position, functionality, size, presentation, and information). The classification and type of intervention implemented for selected articles are provided in [Supplementary Table](#). The type of nudging approach used in the selected articles was outlined on the basis of the intervention focus of selected studies that resulted in 5 different intervention types: availability, position, size, presentation, and information that belonged to either intervention class properties or placement. Furthermore, some of the selected articles used more than 1 nudge type; thus, in this case, the effect of nudges

Figure. Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses flow diagram indicating the selection process of publications.

was analyzed separately and was outlined in more than 1 intervention type and class (Supplementary Table).

The meta-analysis used SPSS software (version 22, IBM, 2013) for computing sample size, *P*, and effect direction for each selected article. The main outcome variables (eg, means, percentage, and total sales of items) of the intervention reported in the 9 articles were included in the meta-analysis. Moreover, some of the selected articles implemented more than 1 nudge and reported more than 1 result; thus, the outcomes were analyzed separately, which resulted in a total of 13 studies for the meta-analysis. The analysis was conducted with continuous outcomes using precalculated effect size using SPSS software. The standard difference in mean, confidence intervals, and *P* were computed for each study. The significance of effect size is based on Cohen's *d*; thus, effect size ≤ 0.2 is small, 0.2–0.5 is medium, and > 0.5 is large.⁴⁴ The result from homogeneity tests shows heterogeneity between the studies; thus, a random-effect model was performed for the meta-analysis as the model presumes that the effects in the studies follow some distribution and are not alike.⁴⁶

RESULTS

Table 1 briefly describes the aim, country, nudging class/type, data analysis method, main findings, outcome measured, study design, length, sample size, and effect sizes of the selected articles. In total, 10 of the study designs were randomized controlled trials, and the length of the intervention varied from 4 days to 2 years. The sample size of the studies was based on the number of participants or meals served. The sample size in some studies was relatively small compared with others; however, all selected articles had > 100 participants, which is the minimum sample size requirement for a meaningful result.⁴⁷ Most studies were conducted in Europe ($n = 11$), whereas the rest ($n = 3$) were conducted in the US. Most articles ($n = 11$) applied altered properties, 2 altered placements, and only 1 altered placement and properties. The effect size estimation for the

Table 1. Summary of Interventional Studies That Applied the Nudging Approach to Promote Sustainable Food Consumption With a Description of the Country, Aim, Nudging Class/Type, Analysis, Findings, Outcome, Design, Length, Sample Size, and Effect Sizes of the Study

Intervention Study	Country	Aim	Intervention Class/Type	Data Analysis	Findings	Outcome	Study Design	Length	Sample Size	Effect Size
Colleoni et al ⁴⁸	Italy	Measure the effectiveness of nudging by making food consumption and lifestyles healthier and more sustainable	Altering placement and properties/position + presentation + information	Factor analysis	The intervention showed increased consumption of healthier and more sustainable food	The simplified information, increased prominence, and framing effect resulted in an increase in consumption of raw vegetables by 50%, and from hot range was increased by 13%	Survey Baseline Intervention Follow-up	5 d 5 d 5 d	2,782 participants 3217 trays	NA
Plester et al ⁴⁹	US	Encourage consumers to eat sustainable foods that have low carbon, nitrogen, and water footprint	Altering properties/information	ANOVA	Information about food sustainability increased purchases of sustainable foods among women but not men	Study 1: Sustainability labels menus with 4 leaves increased the purchase in women from 6% to 38%. Study 2: Implementation of sustainable menu showed an increase in the purchase of veggie burgers among women from 0% to 15%	Intervention Study 1 Study 2	4 d	228 participants 228 participants	0.27
Brunner et al ⁵⁰	Sweden	Investigate how traffic-light labels affect consumer behavior	Altering properties/information	Logistic regression	Information provided through traffic-light labels leads to more climate-friendly food consumption	Traffic-light labeling used to show the carbon footprints of the food items showed a decrease in sales of red-labeled meat items by 4.8% and noted an increase in sales of green-labeled meat items by 11.5%	RCT Control Intervention	28 d 33 d	2,524 participants 2,824 participants	0.05
Vischers and Siegrist ⁵¹	Switzerland	Examine the relationship between consumers' liking of the meal and global warming potential	Altering properties/information	Kendall T coefficient, nonparametric	Introducing the climate-friendly choice label increased the number of climate-friendly meal purchases	Study 1: Rating the taste of the meal showed no significance in the purchase Study 2: Climate-friendly choice labels and information posters resulted in an increase in climate-friendly hot foods by 9.7%	Survey + control Study 1 Study 2	8 d 9 d	225 participants 780 participants	0.22 0.16

(continued)

Table 1. (Continued)

Intervention Study	Country	Aim	Intervention Class/Type	Data Analysis	Findings	Outcome	Study Design	Length	Sample Size	Effect Size
Griesoph et al ⁵²	Germany	Testing the effectiveness of guessed norms and descriptive norms for climate-friendly meal choices	Altering properties/information	Logistic regression	The higher the presumed proportion of vegetarian dishes sold, the lower the probability of choosing a vegetarian dish	The nudging effect of asking customers to guess the norm did not show the significance of promoting climate-friendly meal choice	Survey + Intervention + Survey Control Intervention	4 d	377 participants 797 participants	0.08
Garnett et al ⁵³	United Kingdom	Assessing the impact of nudging on meal selection by increasing the proportion of vegetarian meals	Altering placement/availability	Binominal generalized linear mixed model	The changes to catering practices contributed to achieving more sustainable diets	An observational and experimental field study was conducted in which the proportion of vegetarian meals was increased to nudge meal selection, which showed increases in sales of vegetarian meals by between 41% and 79%, respectively	RCT Study 1 Study 2	140 d 55 d	1394 participants 121 participants	0.21
Campbell-Arvai et al ⁵⁴	US	Investigate the effectiveness of asymmetric default interventions to facilitate proenvironmental behavior	Altering properties/presentation	7-point semantic differential scale (−3 to 3) Binary logistic regression	Default-based interventions motivated consumers toward proenvironmental behavior	The default menu showed appealing or unappealing meat-free options, and a conventional menu resulted in 47.5% in the informed group and 40% in the control group choosing a vegetarian meal when offered an appealing meat-free option, whereas, in the unappealing meat-free menu option, 20% in informed and 7.5% in controlled choose a meat-free meal	Survey Phase I Phase II	1 d 2 wk	26 participants 319 participants	0.37 −0.07
Kurz ⁵⁵	Sweden	Reduce meat consumption by changing the menu order and enhancing the visibility of the vegetarian dish	Altering properties/presentation	Ordinary least square regression, DID estimation	Changing the menu order resulted in consumers choosing more climate-friendly diets	The change in the order of the menu and increase in the visibility of vegetarian food items resulted in a 6% increase in sales of vegetarian lunches	Intervention Baseline Intervention Follow-up	10 wk 17 wk 13 wk	327 dishes 299 dishes 254 dishes	NA
Slapø and Karevold ⁵⁶	Norway	Test the effectiveness of eco-labels with posters to influence consumers to select environmentally friendly options	Altering properties/information	Ordinary least square regression	The traffic-light labels, in combination with posters, can improve eco-friendly food choices in the short term	The traffic-light label used in the first system resulted in a reduction of sales of meat items by 9%, whereas the second and third systems used green and red colors separately to represent the environmental impact of the food item that showed no effect	RCT Control Period 1 Period 2	17 days 20 days 22 days	228 participants	−0.31 −0.16
Spaargaren et al ⁵⁷	Netherland	Study the response of consumers on carbon labels in the canteen	Altering properties/information	Mean	Carbon labels showed a modest impact on behavior	Phase 1: Applying black-and-white carbon labels showed no effect Phase 2: Traffic-light-colored carbon labeling had a modest effect	Intervention vs Control Phase I Phase II Focus group	8 wk 7 wk 1 d	290 participants 13 participants	NA
Lorenz-Walther et al ⁵⁸	Germany	Assess the effect of posters and portion size reduction on plate leftovers	Altering properties/size + information	Structural equation modeling analysis	Portion size reductions resulted in lower levels of plate waste	The experimental intervention that reduced portion size had a small but significant indirect effect on plate leftovers	RCT Baseline Intervention	1 wk 6 wk	503 participants 377 participants	0.16 −0.18

(continued)

Table 1. (Continued)

Intervention Study	Country	Aim	Intervention Class/Type	Data Analysis	Findings	Outcome	Study Design	Length	Sample Size	Effect Size
Andersson and Neilander ⁵⁹	Sweden	Alter the order of the menu to nudge consumers toward more sustainable meal choices	Altering properties/presentation	Ordinary least square regression	Menu modification decreased the share of meat dishes sold	The implementation of menu modification decreased the sales of meat items by 11%	Observational Control Intervention	25 d 25 d	7968 meals	NA
Garnett et al ⁶⁰	United Kingdom	To reduce meat consumption, place vegetarian options first to reduce meat consumption	Altering placement/position	Univariate and multivariate analysis	The relative sales were increased when changing the order of meals	Study 1: The change in the order of meal options resulted in no effect Study 2: Placing the vegetarian option first showed no effect at lunchtime, but sales increased by 2.3% at dinnertime	Experimental Study 1 Study 2	2 y	54745 meals 48912 meals	NA
Jalil et al ⁶¹	US	Examine the effects of an awareness-raising intervention on meat consumption	Altering properties/information	Logit regression	Informing consumers and encouraging voluntary shifts toward plant-based diets can effectively reduce the demand for meat	The treatment group showed a decrease in the purchase of meat-based meals by 4.6%, whereas an increase in the purchase of plant-based meals by 4.2%	RCT Baseline Intervention Follow-up	6 wk 7 wk 13 wk	participants	0.28

ANOVA indicates analysis of variance; DID, difference in difference; NA, not available; RCT, randomized controlled trial.

meta-analysis based on Cohen's *d* shows that most included studies showed medium to small effect sizes.

Table 2 shows the forest plot of the meta-analysis. The overall effect size of Cohen's *d* = 0.06 (95% confidence interval [CI], 0.009–0.063) ($P = 0.27$) was obtained from the random-effect model for the studies using the nudging approach toward sustainable food consumption. The result shows that 5 out of 13 studies show a medium effect size. The studies that showed modest effect size were Piester et al⁴⁹ ($d = 0.27$ [95% CI = 0.011–0.539]), Visschers and Siegrist⁵¹ ($d = 0.22$ [95% CI, 0.081–0.364]); Campbell-Arvai et al⁵⁴ ($d = 0.37$ [95% CI, 0.149–0.597]); Garnett et al⁵³ ($d = 0.21$ [95% CI, 0.067–0.356]) and Jalil et al⁶¹ ($d = 0.28$ [95% CI = 0.011–0.555]). A funnel plot (Supplementary Figure) was used to interpret the publication bias in the study that shows the asymmetrical distribution, indicating that the studies are likely to have publication bias and study heterogeneity.⁶²

Altering placement of the food product: 1 out of 13 articles implemented nudging by altering the placement that showed a highly significant effect ($P = 0.004$) with a medium effect size of $d = 0.21$ (95% CI = 0.067–0.356).⁵³

Altering properties of the food product: 12 out of 13 studies implemented nudging by altering the properties in which the studies that showed significant effect were Jalil et al ($P = 0.04$),⁶³ Lorenz-Walther et al ($P = 0.01$),⁵⁸ Piester et al ($P = 0.04$),⁴⁹ and Visschers and Siegrist ($P < 0.01$)⁵¹ with mostly medium effect sizes $d = 0.27$ (95% CI, 0.011–0.539),⁴⁹ $d = 0.22$ (95% CI, 0.081–0.364),⁵¹ and $d = 0.28$ (95% CI, 0.011–0.555)⁶¹ but low effect size for $d = 0.17$ (95% CI, 0.041–0.307).⁵⁸ A medium effect size $d = 0.37$ (95% CI, 0.149–0.597) with a highly significant effect $P < 0.01$ in study 1 and a small effect size $d = -0.07$ (95% CI, -0.291 to 0.154) with insignificant effect $P = 0.53$ in study 2 were observed.⁵⁰ Other studies did not show any significant effect with very small effect sizes Brunner et al ($P = 0.05$),⁵⁰ Griesoph et al ($P = 0.38$),⁵² Lorenz-Walther et al ($P = 0.07$),⁵⁸ Visschers and Siegrist ($P = 0.24$)⁵¹ and in both phases of study by Slapø and Karevold ($P = 0.10$ and

Table 2. Result of Meta-analysis for Nudging Sustainable Food Consumption

Study Name	Nudging Subgroup	Effect		P	Forest Plot
		Size	95% CI		
Jalil et al ⁶¹	Information	0.28	0.01–0.56	0.04	
Lorenz-Walther et al ⁵⁸	Information	-0.18	-0.38 to 0.02	0.07	
Lorenz-Walther et al ⁵⁸	Size	0.17	0.04–0.31	0.01	
Slapø and Karevold ⁵⁶	Information-I	-0.16	-0.53 to 0.20	0.38	
Slapø and Karevold ⁵⁶	Information-II	-0.31	-0.70 to 0.06	0.10	
Campbell-Arvai et al ⁵⁴	Information	-0.07	-0.29 to 0.15	0.53	
Campbell-Arvai et al ⁵⁴	Presentation	0.37	0.15–0.60	0.001	
Garnett et al ⁵³	Availability	0.21	0.07–0.36	0.004	
Griesoph et al ⁵²	Information	-0.08	-0.26 to 0.10	0.38	
Visschers and Siegrist ⁵¹	Taste rating	-0.16	-0.43 to 0.11	0.24	
Visschers and Siegrist ⁵¹	Information	0.22	0.08–0.36	0.002	
Brunner et al ⁵⁰	Information	0.05	0.00–0.11	0.05	
Piester et al ⁴⁹	Information	0.27	0.01–0.54	0.04	

CI indicates confidence interval.

Note. Model: Random-effect model; Overall effect size: $d = 0.06$; test of overall effect size: $z = 1.10$; $P = 0.27$.

$P = 0.38$).⁵⁶ The overall effect of nudging by altering the properties was not significant ($P = 0.08$), with a small effect size $d = 0.16$.

DISCUSSION

This systematic literature review and meta-analysis aimed to investigate the effectiveness of nudging approaches implemented at the university canteens. Most articles implemented the nudging intervention to achieve behavioral change toward increased environmental sustainability and lower greenhouse gas emissions. Other articles applied behavioral nudges promoting nutritionally balanced food while promoting environmentally friendly behavior. The nudging interventions were classified and type identified according to the TIPPME framework. The framework identified 2 articles that applied altering placement, 11 applied altering properties, and 1 applied altering of properties and placement of the food product. The key outcomes are discussed following the different classes of nudging identified through the TIPPME framework.

Altering Placement of the Food Product

The article by Garnett et al⁵³ implemented nudging by altering the placement that, showed a medium effect size ($d = 0.21$) and reported an increase in

sales of vegetarian meals by 41% in the observational and 79% in the experimental field study. The finding aligns with a previously conducted meta-analysis that reported a medium effect size ($d = 0.39$) when altering the placement of fruits and vegetables.³⁰ Another article by Garnett et al⁶⁰ altered the position by placing the vegetarian option first. The finding showed an increase in the sale of vegetarian options by 2.3% at dinner time but did not show any effect at lunchtime that may have been influenced by other aspects of the choice environment. Previous studies have shown that items displayed at the start and end can significantly influence consumers' cognitive decision-making,^{64,65} and repositioning food items impacted promoting healthy food choices.⁶³ Thus, future interventions aiming to reduce meat consumption could increase the availability of vegetarian options by repositioning food items that may influence consumers' choices.

Altering Properties of the Food Product

A negative effect size ($d = -0.07$) was reported in the article by Campbell-Arvai et al⁵⁴ that provided information on appealing or unappealing meat-free options on the menu. The article evaluated the perceived level of appeal on the basis of Positive and Negative Affect Schedule scales by Watson et al⁶⁶ using a series of bipolar scales, for instance, desirable vs undesirable. Moreover, a

medium effect size ($d = 0.37$) was obtained in the same article when presenting appealing or unappealing meat-free meal options in the default menu that increased the consumption of meat-free options by 89.7%. The findings are similar to what has been observed in previous research that modified menus to promote plant-based meals with dish-of-the-day and other default interventions.^{67,68} Furthermore, the articles by Andersson and Nelander⁵⁹ and Kurz⁵⁵ also implemented menu modifications by increasing the visibility of vegetarian options, which resulted in a significant increase in sales of vegetarian meals. These findings align with previous research showing a willingness to purchase vegetarian foods instead of meat because of menu modifications.^{69,70}

Piester et al⁴⁹ modified the menu using sustainability labels based on the degree of the environmental impact of food items. The application of sustainability labels in the menus reported a medium effect size with a significant increase in the purchase of veggie burgers among women. However, a similar approach has been implemented in supermarkets and restaurants that did not significantly affect consumers' decision-making,^{71,72} indicating that these sustainability labels may create confusion and overload consumers with complex information. Therefore, the nudge types presentation and information could be designed to include

multiple SDGs to influence consumers' decision-making.⁷³⁻⁷⁵

The application of traffic-light labeling as an indicator of the degree of the environmental impact of the food item reported a reduction in meat sales and an increase in sales of the green-labeled meat items; however, no effect was seen when using green and red colors separately.^{50,56} Furthermore, the article by Spaargaren et al⁵⁷ also implemented a black-and-white carbon label that showed no effect in Phase I and only a modest impact in Phase II, in which a colored carbon label (influenced by a traffic light) with comprehensive information was implemented. Previous interventions showed the effectiveness of using traffic-light labeling with additional information⁷⁶ and for a longer time,⁷⁷ leading to positive shifts toward sustainable and healthy choices. Traffic-light labeling triggers consumer responses unconsciously, thus easing the cognitive burden of making informed choices⁷⁸; thus, these efforts could be integrated with redesigning the meal offers for effective nudging toward plant-based meal choices and nutrient intake.³⁵ Therefore, implementing traditional traffic-light labeling, together with some additional information for a more extended period, may boost consumers' awareness to achieve better outcomes in the future.

The article by Visschers and Siegrist⁵¹ implemented a combination of climate-friendly labels and information posters, which increased the purchase of climate-friendly meal choices by 9.7%, showing a medium effect ($d = 0.22$). However, in the same study, a negative effect ($d = -0.16$) was seen when consumers rated the taste of the meal, which was then related to the meal's global warming potential and perceived environmental impacts.

Moreover, the effect of unsustainable food choices on climate change and the benefits of reducing meat consumption was promoted by conducting lectures and providing information in the article by Jalil et al.⁶¹ The article reported a medium effect size ($d = 0.28$) that showed a decrease in the purchase of meat-based meals and a simultaneous increase in the purchase of plant-based meals.

However, the effectiveness of information posters on consumer behaviors showed a negative effect size ($d = -0.18$) in the article by Lorenz-Walther et al.⁵⁸ In contrast, implementing information, education, and posters has previously been used in school canteens as an effective tool.⁷⁹ These differences indicate that the successful use of information as a nudging tool is highly determined by the quality of meals offered at the canteen.³⁵

Furthermore, the article by Griessoph et al⁵² implemented descriptive and guessed norms as a nudging strategy that showed a negative effect size ($d = -0.08$). The descriptive norms were based on how people behave, whereas the guessed norms were interindividually changing guesses of a particular descriptive norm based on an individual mindset about behavioral patterns. The findings from the article show that using guessed norms as a nudging tool did not show any significance in promoting climate-friendly meal choices.

The article by Lorenz-Walther et al⁵⁸ reported a small effect size ($d = 0.17$) with a significant indirect effect of reducing the plate size on plate waste. However, previous research showed that portion size reduction was an effective nudging tool in promoting sustainable consumer behavior at a store.⁸⁰

Altering Placement and Properties of the Food Product

The article by Colleoni et al⁴⁸ implemented 3 different types of nudges, in which altering the position of whole-meal bread and white bread to make the former more visible resulted in a 200% increase in consumption. The study also changed the layout, raised the fruits and vegetable basket, and achieved 50% more consumption of raw vegetables. The study further verified a piece of simple information labeling (ie, so good on healthier food items) that positively influenced canteen users' choices. In addition, varied food choices resulted in less food waste as the amount of unused food was reduced. Thus, future studies could implement a similar approach to prevent food waste in canteens. These nudges were designed on the

basis of findings from a survey exploring eating behaviors instead of implementing random nudges; thus, future studies need to consider implementing nudges after understanding the current behavior of the users.⁸¹

The review has a clear scope and predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria for the type of intervention and study setting. The search strategy for the systematic literature review has followed the requirements of the PRISMA statement. Furthermore, the meta-analysis identified publication biases using a funnel plot, and asymmetry was assessed using the Egger method.

The study has several limitations. First, the study's findings are limited to the few articles studied. Second, the results are based on the primary studies and, thus, carry their limitations. For instance, some of the primary studies reported a loss of individual purchase data, missing data, and data misclassification that could have resulted in measurement errors in the findings of their studies.^{55,59} Furthermore, in the study by Andersson and Nelander,⁵⁹ the meat option was displayed on top of the website menu for 6 weeks, which could have significantly affected the intervention outcome. Finally, Piester et al⁴⁹ fail to explain the long-term effect of sustainable menus and labels on buying sustainable foods, as the purchase is only measured once.

Moreover, some studies did not measure the effect of each nudging tool, limiting an explanation of the impact of nudges separately. Furthermore, because of the lack of previous studies among Danish young adults, the background and comparisons are limited to research conducted among other age groups in Denmark. Finally, a risk of bias assessment could not be conducted for this study as only limited studies have specified the risk of biases in the primary studies.

IMPLICATIONS FOR RESEARCH AND PRACTICE

This study identified 14 articles for the systematic literature review, out of which 9 articles were selected for the meta-analysis. The study identified

increasing availability, modifying the menu, and providing information through labels and lectures as the most effective nudges for promoting sustainable food consumption behavior. The most used nudging types were traffic-light labels/carbon labels and information/posters; however, their effects on behavior are ambiguous. For instance, implementing traditional traffic lights (red, green, and yellow) showed a modest effect, whereas modified traffic-light labels (black-and-white) did not show a significant result.⁵⁷ Furthermore, combining 2 or more nudging strategies effectively yields sustainable food consumption behavior change.^{48,58} Thus, the findings from this review may support designing a nudging strategy that could further verify the integration of multiple nudging strategies for behavioral change and future food policy and guidelines.

In addition, it is important that future studies investigate the effect of integrated nudging strategies over time and their cost-effectiveness. As the primary studies support, it is recommended to prioritize baseline studies for understanding consumer behavior to select appropriate nudging strategies rather than implementing random nudges.^{48,49,51} Practitioners could investigate psychosocial, socio-demographic, and lifestyle factors influencing sustainable food consumption and design targeted nudges to significantly impact consumers' intention to perform sustainable food consumption.^{82–84} This is essential as there might be an attitude-behavior gap in sustainable food consumption as consumers constantly make trade-offs, such as price, health, and nutrition information.⁷¹ These nudging efforts might also be integrated with pricing strategies to influence consumers' purchasing behavior, particularly in university canteens.^{85,86} Finally, future studies might also consider comparing and contrasting the effectiveness of nudging strategies between other forms of canteens, as well as restaurants and grocery stores.

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SUPPLEMENTARY DATA

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